

Sensitive Data Toolkit for Researchers

Part 4: De-identification Guidance

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**Digital Research
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De-identification Guidance

The guidance below is intended to help you minimize disclosure risk when sharing data that may pose risk to human research participants or to other entities. If you use any of the following techniques to de-identify your data, please include this information in a “README” file¹ or other documentation that accompanies your data. For transparency, it should be clear how the dataset was modified to protect study participants. Sensitive data frequently involve data on human participants, but these principles can also apply to data on companies or other entities such as community groups, or scientific information such as the location of endangered species.

Before proceeding, please note that not all human participant data need to be de-identified, or stripped of direct and indirect identifiers. In all cases, data should only be shared to the extent agreed upon in consent documentation. If you are unsure whether you need to de-identify your data or should even share them in the first place, please consult with your institution’s Research Ethics Board. For help selecting a repository for your data, please consult with librarians at your institution to see if support is available.

For help understanding any terms used in this document, please see the Sensitive Data Toolkit’s [Glossary of Terms for Sensitive Data Used for Research Purposes](#).² You may also wish to review the [Human Participant Research Data Risk Matrix](#) and [Research Data Management Language for Informed Consent](#) for more information.³

¹ Harvard, “README Files”, <https://datamanagement.hms.harvard.edu/collect-analyze/documentation-metadata/readme-files>

² Digital Research Alliance of Canada Sensitive Data Working Group., “Sensitive Data Toolkit for Researchers Part 1: Glossary of Terms for Sensitive Data used for Research Purposes,” May 13, 2026, <https://zenodo.org/records/20184871>.

³ Digital Research Alliance of Canada Sensitive Data Working Group., “Sensitive Data Toolkit for Researchers Part 2: Human Participant Research Data Risk Matrix,” May 13, 2026, <https://zenodo.org/records/20185267> , and Digital Research Alliance of Canada Sensitive Data Working Group., “Sensitive Data Toolkit for Researchers Part 3: Research Data Management Language for Informed Consent,” May 13, 2026, <https://zenodo.org/records/20185326>.

Guidance for Quantitative Data

Identify and Remove Direct Identifiers

Direct identifiers are those that uniquely identify an individual or entity within a dataset. Unless explicit consent was received from study participants, they must be removed from any published version of your dataset. The following list is based on one in the text *Research Data Management in the Canadian Context: a Guide for Practitioners and Learners*⁴. Other lists are available including from major international funding agencies, the US Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) and the British Medical Journal. See Preparing raw clinical data for publication: guidance for journal editors, authors, and peer reviewers and List of 18 items considered under HIPAA to be identifiers.⁵ Examples to consider derived from these lists are:

1. Full or partial names or initials
2. Dates linked to individuals, such as birth, graduation, or hospitalization (year alone or month alone may be acceptable)
3. Full or partial addresses (large units of geography, such as city, fall under indirect identifiers and need to be reviewed)
4. Full or partial postal codes (the first three digits may be acceptable)
5. Telephone or fax numbers
6. Email addresses
7. Web or social media identifiers or usernames

⁴ Alisa Beth Rod and Kristi Thompson. "Sensitive Data: Practical and Theoretical Considerations." Chapter in *Research Data Management in the Canadian Context: a Guide for Practitioners and Learners*. Western University, Western Libraries, 2023.

<https://ecampusontario.pressbooks.pub/canadardm/chapter/sensitive-data-practical-and-theoretical-considerations/>

⁵ Iain Hrynaszkiewicz, Melissa L. Norton, Andrew J. Vickers, and Douglas G. Altman, "Preparing Raw Clinical Data for Publication: Guidance for Journal Editors, Authors, and Peer Reviewers." *BMJ* 340 (January 29, 2010): c181, <https://www.bmj.com/content/340/bmj.c181>; and Steve Alder, "What is Considered PHI Under HIPAA Rules?" *HIPAA Journal* (December 28, 2017), <https://www.hipaajournal.com/considered-phi-hipaa/>.

8. Web or Internet protocol numbers, precise browser and operating system information (these may be collected by some types of survey software or web forms)
9. Vehicle identifiers, such as licence plates
10. Identifiers linked to medical or other devices
11. Any other identifying numbers directly or indirectly linked to individuals, such as social insurance numbers, student numbers, or pet ID numbers
12. Photographs of individuals or their houses or locations, or video recordings containing these; medical images or scans
13. Audio recordings of individuals (Han et al., 2020)
14. Biometric data
15. Any unique and recognizable characteristics of individuals (e.g. mayor of Kapuskasing or Nobel prize winner)

In addition, any shared digital files such as photographs or documents should be checked for embedded direct identifiers (e.g. usernames) or identifying metadata⁶, (e.g. IP address, location). Note that this list is not necessarily exhaustive and careful judgement should be exercised in thinking through whether a piece of information constitutes a direct identifier.

How do I remove this information?

Removing direct identifiers from your data is relatively straightforward. You may either A) split your dataset into two databases with direct identifiers retained in one database, and the remaining information to be shared in another. A randomly generated linkage key in each resulting database can be retained which makes reconstruction of the full database possible; or B) delete the identifying data elements entirely. In either case, you should ensure that the file does not contain any version history or other mechanism which would enable someone to restore the full database. Ensure that any processes align with measures detailed in consent documentation. If you are unsure whether data can simply be unlinked or if it must be destroyed, consult your institution's Research Ethics Board.

If the direct identifiers are to be retained at all, they should be kept in a secure location where they can only be accessed in the case of a specific need (for example, to notify participants of an

⁶ "Metadata and Privacy: A Technical and Legal Overview"
https://www.priv.gc.ca/en/opc-actions-and-decisions/research/explore-privacy-research/2014/md_201410/

adverse event). Consider also whether all members of the research team need access to the direct identifiers.

Identify and Evaluate Indirect or Quasi-Identifiers based on Perceived Risk and Utility

Indirect or quasi-identifiers are characteristics (such as demographic information) relating to individuals that may not be identifying on their own but can be disclosive in combination or when combined with other information. For instance, identifying a participant's home community size within an overall limited geographic study area may allow someone to infer that participant's location more precisely. A variable should be considered a quasi-identifier if someone could plausibly match that variable to information from another source. See the [International Household Survey Network Anonymization Principles](#) and the [Information and Privacy Commissioner Ontario De-identification Guidelines for Structured Data](#) for more information on finding and assessing quasi-identifiers.⁷ Note also that in combination, metadata fields that are not direct identifiers could still be indirectly identifying.

A list of potential quasi-identifiers:

- Geographic identifiers (census geography, town name, urban/rural indicator) of home, place of birth, place of treatment, place of schooling, or other geography linked to individuals
- Sex / gender identity, orientation
- Ethnic background, race, visible minority, or Indigenous status
- Immigration status
- Membership in organizations
- Use of specific social networks or services
- Socioeconomic data, such as occupation, place of work, income, or education
- Household and family composition, marital status, number of children / pregnancies
- Criminal records and other information that might be linked to public records
- Generalized dates linked to individuals, e.g. age, graduation year, immigration year

⁷ "Anonymization Principles," International Household Survey Network, accessed August 4, 2020, <https://ihsn.org/node/137>; Information and Privacy Commissioner of Ontario, *Deidentification Guidelines for Structured Data*, Information and Privacy Commissioner of Ontario, October 25, 2025. <https://www.ipc.on.ca/en/resources/de-identification-guidelines-structured-data> .

- Some text responses
 - Note: These must be checked individually. For instance, the comment “The library should be open longer” is not identifying; however, a comment like “As chair of a research group that uses the library,...” is potentially identifying.
- Some medical information (e.g. permanent disabilities or rare medical conditions) may be identifying; temporary illness or injury is less likely to be identifying. If the information can be found in other databases it has greater potential to re-identify the person.

How do I figure out what combination of quasi-identifiers could be problematic?

1. Extreme Values

As a first pass, a data curator or researcher might look at the variables in isolation and consider them in context with other information about the data. Extreme or unusual values (e.g. age over 90 years, high income or a large number of children) can pose risk. These can be assessed by looking at frequency distributions and histograms.

2. Observe the possible combinations

A good first step may be to look at the variables in the dataset and consider describing an individual to a friend using only the values of those variables. Is there any likelihood that the person would be recognizable? For example, “I’m thinking of a person living in Toronto who is female, married, has a University degree, is between the ages of 40 and 55 and has an income of between 60 and 75 thousand dollars.” Even if there is only one such person in the dataset, this is likely not enough information to create risk UNLESS contextual information about the dataset narrows things down further. For instance, if your data are limited to a narrow group of individuals, such as the referees for the Ontario Hockey League, the list of quasi-identifiers given above may be enough to uniquely identify an individual. Quasi-identifiers need to be evaluated in the context of what is known or what may be reasonably inferred about the population represented by the data.

3. Assess combinations mathematically

K-anonymity is a mathematical approach to demonstrating that a dataset has been de-identified. “K” is an integer selected by the researcher that represents a group of records with the same

information across all quasi-identifiers.⁸ Within your dataset, such a set of 'k' records (e.g., a set of 3 or 5 records) is called an equivalence class. To achieve k-anonymity, it should not be possible to distinguish one record from the other records in its equivalence class. For example, if you choose a k value of 5, each record in your dataset must have the exact set of quasi-identifiers that are present in at least 4 other records in order to achieve k-anonymity.

K-anonymity only works to precisely estimate risk if a dataset is a complete sample of the population. K-anonymity considerably overestimates risk in the case of a dataset that is a subsample of a population. When determining the appropriate k value to use, consider:

- A lower k value may be sufficient in datasets that contain small samples from a large population.
- The sensitivity of the dataset in general also needs to be considered. If the data have a high potential to cause harm to participants, a higher value of k may be appropriate.

Keep in mind that a dataset that is a complete sample of a known population may have additional risk factors. Imagine that all the respondents in a particular equivalence class answered a question the same way - you would know how each person in the survey belonging to that equivalence class answered the question. Respondents to surveys are generally told that their responses will be kept confidential, not merely that no one will know which line of data contains their specific answers. A k-anonymous dataset that is a complete sample may not fulfill that promise.

Even if k-anonymity greatly overestimates risk, as in the case of a small sample from a large population, low k values allow the researcher to isolate potentially risky combinations of variables for further scrutiny.

The code in Appendix 1 can be used with your preferred statistical software package to create equivalence classes based on the quasi-identifiers in the dataset and to list them by size. If any equivalence class has fewer members than the value of k you selected, use the data reduction techniques below to further reduce dataset risk.

For more on k-anonymity, see [International Household Survey Network \(IHSN\)'s Measuring the Disclosure Risk](#).⁹

⁸ Khaled El Emam and Fida Kamal Dankar, "Protecting Privacy Using k-Anonymity," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 15, no. 5 (September 2008): 627–637, <https://doi.org/10.1197/jamia.M2716>.

⁹ "Measuring the Disclosure Risk," International Household Survey Network, accessed August 4, 2020, <https://ihsn.org/anonymization-risk-measure>.

4. Data reduction techniques to address dataset risk

Univariate frequencies and bivariate crosstabs can be used to identify small¹⁰ categories of quasi-identifiers. Data reduction techniques can be used to mitigate risk once you have identified these small groups. There are three simple types of data reduction you may wish to consider:

1. The simplest is to completely drop risky variables from the dataset. This is an option for variables with relatively high risk that are not considered to be of high research value. (For example, in some datasets geography may be considered relatively less important than ethnicity or language.)
2. The second is global re-coding, or aggregating the observed values into a defined set of classes, such as transforming a variable with years of age into a variable of ten-year age categories, or top-coding a high income category to “\$100,000 and above”.
3. A third option for unusual cases is to use local suppression. For example, a very young married respondent might have their marital status set to ‘missing’ as an alternative to globally re-coding the otherwise non-risky age variable into a larger group. Consider whether any code you share or descriptions of these transformations make it possible to guess the original value of suppressed observations.

After each exercise in data reduction, repeat the test for k-anonymity described above and check equivalence classes until all groups are larger than the selected value of k.

For information on additional techniques, see Component 7 of the [UK Anonymisation Network’s Anonymization Decision-Making Framework](#)¹¹ and Appendix G of [De-Identification Guidelines for Structured Data](#)¹².

Guidance for Qualitative Data

Qualitative data describes qualities or characteristics that can be observed, but not necessarily measured. These types of data are collected through interviews, surveys, or observations, and may be in the form of transcripts, notes, video and audio recordings, images, and text documents. As with quantitative data, direct identifiers may appear in the form of names, date and place of birth, other locations, and even photos. These direct identifiers can be used along with indirect or quasi-identifiers, such as medical, education, financial, and employment information, to trace or determine an individual’s identity.

¹⁰ ‘Small’ is relative; as a first pass, groups smaller than 5% of the dataset or containing fewer than 20 cases could be considered.

¹¹ Elliot, Mackey, O’Hara, and Tudor, *The Anonymisation Decision-Making Framework*.

¹²Information and Privacy Commissioner of Ontario. *De-Identification Guidelines for Structured Data*.

The process for removing identifying information in a video recording, audio interview, or oral transcript is very different from that used to de-identify a medical record or quantitative survey response. For one, it is harder to do programmatically. Extremely detailed field notes or audiovisual information often requires someone to read or watch the content thoroughly.

General Advice

- Avoid asking for identifying information during data collection..
 - It is easier to edit the information at the point of capture than it is to remove information after it has been recorded.
 - If you require identifying information at the research stage, try to capture it within the first few minutes of an interview or recording, so that it is easy to edit it out quickly. Alternatively, transcribe the information in a separate document that can be removed from a person's file.
- Make de-identification part of the process of informed consent.
 - Ensure that study participants are aware of your planned use of the data, and the fact that their information may be de-identified to protect them. Make it clear in your consent forms how extensively they will be de-identified (i.e., what elements will be replaced or removed). While direct identifiers may be eliminated (name, address, birthday, etc.), there may be other subtle clues to their identities that remain within the recording or transcript.
 - Agree in advance with participants which type of identifying information can be revealed in an interview. (For example, the participant may not wish to mention an employer's name). This is easier than removing information after the fact.
 - Keep in mind that not all data need to be de-identified. In some circumstances you may be recording deeply personal accounts and should be mindful of a participant's right to have their story told in their own words. Some participants may have a personal interest in staying identified.

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- Use pseudonyms and change identifying details to protect anonymity.
 - If changing the person's name, location of residence, or occupation can be done without compromising the dataset, this can help to protect their anonymity. Be advised that this could influence the utility of a dataset as it may alter a future researcher's perception of the interviewee.
- If necessary, remove blocks of sensitive text or edit out portions within audio-visual data.
 - Some portion of the research may need to be redacted. Be wary of using search and replace techniques as it is easy to replace the wrong piece of information or to miss things that aren't communicated using typical word choices.
 - Voices in audio recordings may need to be masked by altering pitches.
 - Faces in visual data may need to be pixelated.
- Restrict access.
 - This is not preferred, but some datasets will not remain useful if all identifiers are removed. Where consent permits, it may be possible to allow researchers seeking secondary access to request that queries be performed by the original research team, who can then share results if they are non-disclosive or can be appropriately de-identified. Alternatively, a set of pre-conditions could be set up (such as a research proposal and REB approval) that would permit another researcher to access the data directly assuming that this was made clear to participants during the informed consent process. See the [informed consent guidance](#) for more details.

Note: online AI tools should generally not be used to de-identify qualitative data as the services generally keep a record of queries (which would contain the raw qualitative responses). In general services that may make use of cloud based storage or processing should be carefully evaluated before use.

For more information, see the [UK Data Service's Anonymising Qualitative Data](#).¹³

¹³ "Anonymising Qualitative Data," UK Data Service, last modified June 30, 2020, <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/learning-hub/research-data-management/anonymisation/anonymising-qualitative-data/>

Brief Considerations for Social Media, Medical Images, and Genomics Data

Data collected from social media or social networking platforms (e.g. Facebook).

Although information on social networking sites may be free to access or view, it does not automatically follow that it is free to redistribute. Many platforms have terms of use that you will need to abide by, and the people who use the platform may have an expectation of privacy which must be respected. Some platforms require users to register before content is visible, and others may have terms that prohibit data collection, data scraping, or republishing content elsewhere.

Here are a series of questions to consider before you share social media data:

- Could the topic you are studying be considered sensitive?
- Could your data lead to stigmatization of, or discrimination against, the content author?
- Is the study population vulnerable?
- What expectation of privacy might the individual users of this platform have?
- Is it possible or reasonable to obtain informed consent?
- Can or should the data be de-identified?
- Do the platform's terms of use allow you to redistribute content?

The following resources provide more in-depth guidance:

- Zeffiro and Brodeur, Social Media Research Data Ethics and Management (slides from a workshop presented at McMaster University).¹⁴
- Toronto Metropolitan University Research Ethics Board's Guidelines for Research Involving Social Media.¹⁵

¹⁴ Andrea Zeffiro and Jay Brodeur, "Social Media Research Data Ethics and Management." Workshop presented March 5, 2020, Sherman Centre for Digital Scholarship, McMaster University, <https://macsphere.mcmaster.ca/handle/11375/25327>.

¹⁵Toronto metropolitan University Research Ethics Board, "Guidelines for Research Involving Social Media," Toronto Metropolitan University, November, 2017, <https://www.torontomu.ca/content/dam/research/documents/ethics/guidelines-for-research-involving-social-media.pdf>

- Mannheimer and Hull, Sharing Selves: Developing an Ethical Framework for Curating Social Media Data.¹⁶

North Carolina State University's site contains guidance on the legal and ethical implications of sharing social media data, and an annotated bibliography with further resources.

Medical Images

Images, particularly those from medical software can be a source of hard-to-eliminate personally identifying information (see the Radiological Society of North America guidance)¹⁷. Before you archive medical images, remove any direct identifiers you do not have explicit consent to share, such as name, patient ID, and exact dates from the image header or embedded metadata, and black out any pixels in the image that contain identifying information. Neuroimages must also be defaced using a tool such as PyDeface.¹⁸

The following resources provide more guidance for de-identifying Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) files:

- The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA) De-identification Overview.¹⁹
 - See specifically “Table 1 - DICOM Tags Modified or Removed at the source site” for a list of DICOM tags deemed to be unsafe.
- The Radiological Society of North America (RSNA) International Covid-19 Open Radiology Database (RICORD) De-identification Protocol.²⁰

¹⁶ Sara Mannheimer and Elizabeth Hull, “Sharing Selves: Developing an Ethical Framework for Curating Social Media Data,” *International Journal of Digital Curation* 12, no. 2 (April 18, 2018), <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v12i2.518>.

¹⁷ <https://www.rsna.org/-/media/Files/RSNA/Practice-Tools/RemovingPHI.pdf>

¹⁸ Some repositories may be able to assist you or recommend tools for defacing. For example, the International Neuroimaging Data-Sharing Initiative (INDI) can help researchers who plan to share their data on the INDI platform. For further information, see the INDI *Data Contribution Guide*, accessed August 31, 2020, http://fcon_1000.projects.nitrc.org/indi/indi_data_contribution_guide.pdf.

¹⁹ Kirby, Justin. “Submission and De-identification Overview.” The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA), University of Arkansas for Medical Sciences, April 27, 2020, <https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/Public/Submission+and+De-identification+Overview>.

²⁰ “RSNA International Covid-19 Open Radiology Database (RICORD) De-identification Protocol,” Radiological Society of North America, International COVID-19 Open Radiology Database, accessed August 10, 2020, <https://www.rsna.org/-/media/Files/RSNA/Covid-19/RICORD/RSNA-Covid-19-Deidentification-Protocol.pdf>.

- The DICOM standard itself provides important guidance for de-identifying header information. Specifically, DICOM Part 15: Security and System Management Profiles, Appendix E: Attribute Confidentiality Profiles may be useful.²¹
 - These profiles attempt to balance the need to protect privacy with the need to retain information so the data remain useful.
 - If it is necessary to retain identifiers, your REB application will have ideally referenced the profile you intend to use, and your consent form should clearly state what information will be shared.

De-identification of DICOM files may be done programmatically, using software to strip identifiers from the header.

- TCIA recommends the Clinical Trial Processor (CTP) software developed by RSNA.²²
- RSNA's Covid-19 Open Radiology Database (RICORD) recommends another RSNA software called Anonymizer, and has published instructions on how to install and use it.²³ Anonymizer implements RICORD's de-identification protocol.²⁴
- There are other non-commercial options available, such as the DicomCleanerTM tool.²⁵
- As with all de-identification software, results may be variable, and you should confirm that identifying information was removed before you share your images. Note that:
 - Vendors or end-users may not have always used DICOM elements in a way that conforms to the standard.

²¹ Medical Imaging & Technology Alliance, DICOM Standards Committee, "DICOM Part 15: Security and System Management Profiles." *DICOM Standard* (Arlington, VA: National Electrical Manufacturers Association), accessed August 4, 2020, <https://www.dicomstandard.org/current/>.

²² "Clinical trial processor (CTP)," Radiological Society of North America, Medical Imaging Resource Community (MIRC), accessed August 4, 2020, <https://www.rsna.org/research/imaging-research-tools>.

²³ "RSNA COVID-19 DICOM Data Anonymizer," Radiological Society of North America, International COVID-19 Open Radiology Database, accessed August 10, 2020, <https://www.rsna.org/-/media/Files/RSNA/Covid-19/RICORD/RSNA-Anonymizer-Program-Instructions.pdf>.

²⁴ "RSNA International Covid-19 Open Radiology Database (RICORD) De-identification Protocol," Radiological Society of North America, International COVID-19 Open Radiology Database.

²⁵ Clunie, David A., "DicomCleanerTM," PixelMed PublishingTM, accessed July 16, 2020, <http://www.dclunie.com/pixelmed/software/webstart/DicomCleanerUsage.html>.

- Private elements or private tags may have been used to store personal information, and the use of these tags may not be well-defined in the vendor documentation.

Genomics data, and other biomedical samples

Because each person's DNA sequence is unique, human biological materials can never be truly anonymous. Before you archive or biobank these data, please ensure your plans are consistent with your consent documentation. Ideally the consent process will have:

- Provided participants with information about how their data will be used, analyzed, stored and shared,
- Identified what information will be stored alongside the data,
- Communicated what level of privacy or confidentiality a participant may expect, and who may have access to the data,
- Indicated whether the data/samples will be stored in Canada or outside of Canada,
- Acknowledged whether there is a possibility that the data will be used for commercial purposes,
- Clearly explained the risks of disclosure.

Further information is available in TCPS 2 (2022), Chapter 12: Human Biological Materials Including Materials Related to Human Reproduction (sections A and D specifically), and Chapter 13: Human Genetic Research.²⁶ See also Thorogood (2018) Canada: will privacy rules continue to favour open science?²⁷

²⁶ Government of Canada (Canadian Institutes of Health Research, the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada, and the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council), *Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans, 2022*, https://ethics.gc.ca/eng/policy-politique_tcps2-eptc2_2022.html.

²⁷ Adrian Thorogood, "Canada: Will Privacy Rules Continue to Favour Open Science?" *Human Genetics* 137: 595–602 (July 16, 2018), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00439-018-1922-z>.

Appendix 1: Code for Checking K-Anonymity

-- Stata --

* Stata code for checking k-anonymity

* Kristi Thompson, May 2020

* create the equivalence groups

```
egen equivalence_group= group(var1 var2 var3 var4 var5)
```

* create a variable to count cases in each equivalence group

```
sort equivalence_group
```

```
by equivalence_group: gen equivalence_size =_N
```

* list the ID numbers of equivalence groups containing 3 or fewer cases

```
tab equivalence_group if equivalence_size < 3, sort
```

* list the values of the quasi-identifiers for each small equivalence class.

```
list var1 var2 var3 var4 var5 if equivalence_group == 1
```

--- R --²⁸

```
# R code for checking k-anonymity
```

```
# Carolyn Sullivan and Kristi Thompson, May 2020
```

```
# install plyr, a useful data manipulation package.
```

```
install.packages("plyr")
```

```
# Load the library.
```

²⁸ Note that if you are working in R it is worth investigating the SDCMicro package in R as it has additional features that may be useful.


```
library('plyr')

datafile <- " location of the data file - csv format - "

# Read the csv file.

df <- read.csv (datafile)

# Figure out what equivalence classes there are, and how many cases in each equivalence
class.

dfunique <- ddpby(df, .(var1, var2, var3, var4, var5), nrow)

dfunique <- dfunique[order(dfunique$V1),]

View(dfunique)
```

— Python —

this code assumes you have a Pandas dataframe called “df”

```
# Step 1: Create the equivalence group (grouping by var1, var2, var3, var4, var5)
df['equivalence_group'] = df.groupby(['var1', 'var2', 'var3', 'var4', 'var5']).ngroup()

# Step 2: Create a variable to count cases in each equivalence group
df['equivalence_size'] = df.groupby('equivalence_group')['equivalence_group'].transform('size')

# Step 3: List the equivalence groups that have 3 or fewer cases
small_groups = df[df['equivalence_size'] <= 3]

print("Equivalence groups with 3 or fewer cases:")

print(small_groups[['equivalence_group', 'equivalence_size']].drop_duplicates())

# Step 4: List the values of quasi-identifiers for each small equivalence class. For example, look
at the first equivalence group group_id = 1

print(f"\nValues for equivalence group {group_id}:")

print(df[df['equivalence_group'] == group_id][['var1', 'var2', 'var3', 'var4', 'var5']])
```


The [UK Anonymisation Network's Anonymisation Decision-Making Framework](#), appendix B has instructions for doing this in Excel.²⁹

²⁹ Elliot, Mackey, O'Hara, and Tudor, *The Anonymisation Decision-Making Framework*.

Appendix 2: Free De-identification Software Packages

Many of these tools take a hierarchical approach to de-identifying data, which means that you will need to pre-define possible generalizations for the quasi-identifiers in the dataset. The program will search for possible solutions and recommend a set of the generalizations to use to best meet anonymization goals. For datasets with a large number of quasi-identifiers, or cases where several datasets with similar quasi-identifiers need to be de-identified, this might be a useful approach. For smaller datasets, it may be more straightforward to work in a statistical package. These software packages have fairly steep learning curves if you want to utilize them fully.

Recommended tools:

- Amnesia
 - This software has both online and desktop versions, however, uploading sensitive data to a third-party web site is not recommended. For this reason, it is preferable to download and install the software locally (Windows or Linux only).
 - Amnesia supports k-anonymity and k^m -anonymity (a slightly more flexible approach to anonymity when the number of quasi-identifiers in a dataset is very high, as it allows for combinations up to m quasi-identifiers to appear at least k times in the published data).
 - A few limitations: there is not currently a way to specify missing values; documentation could be more thorough, for instance, defining hierarchies is not straightforward.
 - This software may work best for clinical data, or data which are not survey data.
- sdcMicro
 - An R package for statistical disclosure control (microdata anonymization). This software can read many data types (e.g., csv, sav, dta, sas7bdat, xlsx) and can be used in Windows, Linux, or Mac operating systems. sdcMicro Implements muArgus code.
 - A graphical user interface is available, and there is a vignette with guidance called 'Using the interactive GUI - sdcApp' linked from the sdcMicro landing page in CRAN repository.³⁰ This may be the most user-friendly way to de-identify the data.

³⁰ "Using the interactive GUI – sdcApp, The Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN), accessed August 31, 2020, <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sdcMicro/vignettes/sdcMicro.html>.

- Large datasets take time to load, and computation time for large or complex datasets may be lengthy.³¹
- The Statistical Disclosure Control for Microdata practice guide section on SDC with sdcMicro in R may be helpful if you need further guidance installing and using the sdcMicro package, or see Benschop's sdcMicro GUI manual Documentation.³²

References

1. Alder, Steve. "What is Considered PHI Under HIPAA Rules?" HIPAA Journal, December 28, 2017. <https://www.hipaajournal.com/considered-phi-hipaa/>.
2. Benschop, Thijs, and Matthew Welch. "Statistical Disclosure Control for Microdata: A Practice Guide for sdcMicro." International Household Survey Network. Accessed August 10, 2020. <https://sdcppractice.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>.
3. Clunie, David A. "DicomCleaner™." PixelMed Publishing™. Accessed July 16, 2020. <http://www.dclunie.com/pixelmed/software/webstart/DicomCleanerUsage.html>.
4. El Emam, Khaled, and Fida Kamal Dankar. "Protecting Privacy Using k-Anonymity." Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association 15, no. 5 (September 2008): 627–637. <https://doi.org/10.1197/jamia.M2716>.
5. Elliot, Mark, Elaine Mackey, Kieron O'Hara. The Anonymisation Decision-Making Framework 2nd Edition. UK Anonymisation Network (UKAN). University of Manchester. 2020. <https://ukanon.net/framework/>.
6. Government of Canada (Canadian Institutes of Health Research, the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada, and the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council). Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans. December 2018. https://ethics.gc.ca/eng/policy-politique_tcps2-eptc2_2022.html.
7. Gulban, Omer Faruk, Dylan Nielson, Russ Poldrack, John Lee, Chris Gorgolewski, Vanessasaurus, and Satrajit Ghosh. "Poldracklab/pydeface: V2.0.2." Zenodo. July 19, 2022. <https://zenodo.org/records/6856482>.

³¹ "Computation time," SDC with sdcMicro in R: Setting Up Your Data and more, SDC Practice Guide, 2019, <https://sdcppractice.readthedocs.io/en/latest/sdcMicro.html#computation-time>.

³² "Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC): An Introduction," SDC Practice Guide, 2019, https://sdcppractice.readthedocs.io/en/latest/SDC_intro.html; and Thijs Benschop and Matthew Welch. *Statistical Disclosure Control for Microdata: A Practice Guide for sdcMicro*, International Household Survey Network, accessed August 10, 2020, <https://sdcppractice.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>.

8. Hrynaszkiewicz, Iain, Melissa L. Norton, Andrew J. Vickers, and Douglas G. Altman. "Preparing Raw Clinical Data for Publication: Guidance for Journal Editors, Authors, and Peer Reviewers." *BMJ* 340 (January 29, 2010): c181. <https://www.bmj.com/content/340/bmj.c181>.
9. Information and Privacy Commissioner Ontario. Deidentification Guidelines for Structured Data. Information and Privacy Commissioner of Ontario. October 15, 2025. <https://www.ipc.on.ca/en/resources/de-identification-guidelines-structured-data>
10. International Household Survey Network. "Anonymization Principles." Accessed August 4, 2020. <https://ihsn.org/node/137>.
11. International Household Survey Network. "Measuring the Disclosure Risk." Accessed August 4, 2020. <https://ihsn.org/anonymization-risk-measure>.
12. International Neuroimaging Data-Sharing Initiative (INDI). Data Contribution Guide. Accessed August 4, 2020. http://fcon_1000.projects.nitrc.org/indi/indi_data_contribution_guide.pdf.
13. Kirby, Justin. "Submission and De-identification Overview." The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA), University of Arkansas for Medical Sciences. April 27, 2020. <https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/Public/Submission+and+De-identification+Overview>.
14. Mannheimer, Sara, and Elizabeth Hull. "Sharing Selves: Developing an Ethical Framework for Curating Social Media Data." *International Journal of Digital Curation* 12, no. 2 (April 18, 2018). <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v12i2.518>.
15. Medical Imaging & Technology Alliance, DICOM Standards Committee. "DICOM Part 15: Security and System Management Profiles." In DICOM Standard. Arlington, VA: National Electrical Manufacturers Association. Accessed August 4, 2020. <https://www.dicomstandard.org/current/>.
16. Moore, Stephen M., David R. Maffitt, Kirk E. Smith, Justin S. Kirby, Kenneth W. Clark, John B. Freymann, Bruce A. Vendt, Lawrence R. Tarbox, and Fred W. Prior. "De-identification of Medical Images with Retention of Scientific Research Value." *RadioGraphics* 35, no. 3 (May 13, 2015). <https://doi.org/10.1148/rg.2015140244>.
17. North Carolina State University Libraries. "Social Media Archives Toolkit." Accessed August 4, 2020. <https://www.lib.ncsu.edu/social-media-archives-toolkit>.
18. Portage COVID-19 Working Group, "Can I Share My Data?" September 25, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4041660>.

19. Portage COVID-19 Working Group. "Documentation and Supporting Materials Required for Deposit." September 25, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4042033>.
20. Portage COVID-19 Working Group. "Recommended Repositories." September 25, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4042036>.
21. Digital Research Alliance of Canada Sensitive Data Working Group. "Sensitive Data Toolkit for Researchers Part 1: Glossary of Terms for Sensitive Data used for Research Purposes." May 13, 2026. <https://zenodo.org/records/20184871>.
22. Digital Research Alliance of Canada Sensitive Data Working Group. "Sensitive Data Toolkit for Researchers Part 2: Human Participant Research Data Risk Matrix." May 13, 2026. <https://zenodo.org/records/20185267>.
23. Digital Research Alliance of Canada Sensitive Data Working Group. "Sensitive Data Toolkit for Researchers Part 3: Research Data Management Language for Informed Consent." May 13, 2026. <https://zenodo.org/records/20185326>
24. Radiological Society of North America, International COVID-19 Open Radiology Database. "RSNA International Covid-19 Open Radiology Database (RICORD) De-identification Protocol." Accessed August 10, 2020. <https://www.rsna.org/-/media/Files/RSNA/Covid-19/RICORD/RSNA-Covid-19-Deidentification-Protocol.pdf>.
25. Radiological Society of North America, International COVID-19 Open Radiology Database. "RSNA COVID-19 DICOM Data Anonymizer." Accessed August 10, 2020. <https://www.rsna.org/-/media/Files/RSNA/Covid-19/RICORD/RSNA-Anonymizer-Program-Instructions.pdf>.
26. Radiological Society of North America, Medical Imaging Resource Community (MIRC). "Clinical trial processor (CTP)." Accessed August 4, 2020. <https://www.rsna.org/research/imaging-research-tools>.
27. Toronto Metropolitan University Research Ethics Board. "Guidelines for Research Involving Social Media." Toronto Metropolitan University. November, 2017. <https://www.torontomu.ca/content/dam/research/documents/ethics/guidelines-for-research-involving-social-media.pdf>
28. UK Data Service. "Anonymising Qualitative Data." Last modified June 30, 2020. <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/learning-hub/research-data-management/anonymisation/anonymising-qualitative-data>.

29. Zeffiro, Andrea, and Jay Brodeur. "Social Media Research Data Ethics and Management." Workshop presented April 5, 2018. Sherman Centre for Digital Scholarship. McMaster University. <http://hdl.handle.net/11375/25327>.